

PRESS RELEASE

EU funded projects collaboration for digital transition in the construction sector announced!

All four **LC-008-EEB** funded projects **BIMprove**, **COGITO**, **ASHVIN** and **BIM2TWIN**, agreed on joining forces for raising awareness around **Digital Building Twins** and its impact in the construction industry. Their primary aim is to share **knowledge, experiences and research outcomes** with other stakeholders and communities around the EU and beyond, via online communication like webinars, newsletters, social media channels and scientific or technical articles.

The reason why **European countries** are not convinced to use digital tools in the construction sector is they are still waiting for clear demonstrations of its tangible benefits.

The **lack of commonly agreed standards** and **low interoperability** among collected data reveal a **major drawback to the enterprises' digital transformation**, even for large construction enterprises with full access to state of the art digital, reality capture tools.

The concept of **construction phase digitalization** must deal with seamless communication technologies that enable interconnected objects and people share information to attain the common goals collaboratively.

For these reasons, the new collaboration aims at delivering the wide range of digital tools for the construction sector needed on the European market and raise awareness about the benefits coming from their use.

If you are interested in the topic of building **Digital Twins** and want to know more about developed tools, **visit our websites**, follow our **social media channels**, subscribe to our **newsletters** to stay tuned!

All for projects have received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme, under topic **LC-008-EEB**.

Find our more about our projects:

- **COGITO** project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958310
- **BIMprove** project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958450
- **ASHVIN** project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958161
- **BIM2TWIN** project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958398